

Oxidative Addition Reactions of Tin(II) Oxinates*

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Bis (5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato) tin (II), bis (5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato) tin (II) and bis (5,7-diiodo-8-quinolinolato) tin (II), have been synthesized by the reaction of anhydrous SnCl₂ and the appropriate 5,7-disubstituted-8-quinolinol and characterised from their elemental analysis, i.r., u.v. and visible spectral data. Tin (II) bis oxinates readily react with diphenyldisulphide, PhSSPh, dibenzoylperoxide, (PhCO)₂O₂, iodine monochloride, ICl, halogens, etc. to yield the corresponding tin(IV) chelates. The reactions with PhSSPh and (PhCO)₂O₂ provide a route to the synthesis of new tin(IV) mixed ligand complexes. The i.r., u.v. and visible spectral data for some of the oxidative addition reaction products are also presented and discussed.

At present, very little is known about reactions of organotin(II) and organic tin(II) compounds. The nature of the products resulting from the direct interaction of divalent tin species with organic halides, halogens, etc. is a topic of current interest¹⁻³. Although the preparations of some monomeric organic tin(II) compounds containing Sn-OC bonds⁴⁻⁶, organotin compounds such as dicyclopentadienyl tin(II)⁷ and their reactions with n-alkyl halides have been reported, the behaviour of tin(II) oxinates towards diphenyldisulphide, dibenzoylperoxide, iodine monochloride, halogens, etc. have not been studied. As a part of our general investigations on tin(II) chelates, it was thought worthwhile to study the oxidative addition reactions of tin(II) bisoxinate and tin(II) bis-5,7-disubstituted oxinates. The results of our investigations are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Anhydrous tin(II)chloride was prepared by dehydration of reagent grade tin(II)chloride dihydrate, SnCl₂·2H₂O, by reaction with acetic anhydride⁸ and stored in a tightly closed ground glass bottle. Iodine monochloride and 5,7-disubstituted-8-quinolinols were prepared by the literature methods⁹⁻¹². Solvents were purified and dried prior to use. All the other chemicals used were of reagent grade. I.R. spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 221 spectrophotometer. The ultraviolet and visible spectra were recorded on a Unicam S. P. 500 spectrophotometer.

1. *Bis(8-quinolinolato)tin(II)* was prepared by the reported method¹³

2. *Bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)tin(II)*. Tin(II) chloride (1.89 g, 0.01 mole) dissolved in absolute alcohol (25 ml) was added with stirring to a solution of 5, 7-dichloro-8-quinolinol (4.28 g, 0.02 mole) in alcohol (250 ml). Stirring was continued for about 30 minutes and the pH of the mixture was adjusted to 6.0-6.5 by the addition of dilute ammonia (1:4) or saturated sodium

acetate solution (5 g in 5 ml). The yellow precipitate formed was collected on a filter under suction, washed with alcohol and dried under vacuum. Yield, 50%. Anal. Found : C, 38.92 ; H, 1.75 ; Sn ; 21.78%. Calcd. for C₁₈H₈N₂O₂Cl₄Sn : C, 39.66 ; H, 1.469 ; Sn, 21.79%.

3. *Bis(5, 7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)tin(II)* was prepared by following essentially the above experimental procedure from SnCl₂ (1.89 g, 0.01 mole) and 5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinol (6.06 g, 0.02 mole). The bright yellow precipitate was collected and dried. Yield, 55%. Anal. Found : C, 29.07, H, 1.43, Sn 16.1%. Calcd. for C₁₈H₈N₂O₂Br₄Sn : C, 29.9 ; H, 1.1 ; Sn. 16.43%.

4. *Bis(5,7-diiodo-8-quinolinolato)tin(II)* : Tin(II) chloride (1.89 g, 0.01 mole) in alcohol (50 ml) was added to a suspension of 5,7-diiodo-8-quinolinol(7.94 g), 0.02 mole) and the mixture was refluxed for four hours. The pale brown precipitate obtained on cooling, was collected on a filter under suction, washed with alcohol and dried. Yield, 60%. Anal. Found : C, 23.75 ; H, 1.28 ; Sn, 13.7%. Calcd. for C₁₈H₈N₂O₂I₄Sn : C, 23.75 ; H, 0.89, Sn, 13.04%.

5. *Dithiophenolato bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato) tin(IV)*. Bis-(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato) tin(II) (2.72 g, 0.005 mole) in benzene (100 ml) and diphenyldisulphide (1.09 g, 0.005 mole) in benzene (30 ml) were mixed together and refluxed for four hours. The yellow precipitate obtained was collected, washed with benzene (10 ml) and dried under vacuum. Yield, 60%. Anal. Found : C, 48.71 ; H, 3.11 ; Sn 15.3%. Calcd. for C₃₀H₁₈N₂O₂Cl₄S₂Sn : C, 47.2 ; H, 2.36, Sn, 15.56%.

6. *Dithiophenolato bis(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato) tin(IV)* was obtained by refluxing a mixture of bis (5, 7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato) tin(II) (3.61 g, 0.005 mole) in benzene (100 ml) and diphenyldisulphide (1.09 g, 0.005 mole) in benzene (50 ml). The other experimental

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details were the same as above. Yield 60%. Anal. Found: C, 38.74; H, 2.41, Sn, 12.3%. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{18}N_2O_2Br_4S_2Sn$: C, 38.27; H, 1.914; Sn, 12.62%.

7. *Monothiophenolato*tris(8-quinolinolato)tin(IV): Bis(8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (2.03 g, 0.005 mole) in benzene (150 ml) and diphenyldisulfide (1.09 g, 0.005 mole) in benzene (50 ml) were mixed together and refluxed. The other experimental details were the same as in 5. Yield, 40%. Anal. Found: C, 61.15; H, 4.08; Sn, 17.65; Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{23}N_3O_3Sn$: C, 60.02; H, 3.48; Sn, 17.99%.

8. *Dibenzoato-bis* (8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) Bis(8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (0.812 g, 0.002 mole) in benzene (150 ml) was added to benzoylperoxide (0.48 g, 0.002 mole) in benzene (50 ml) at room temperature. The mixture was stirred for about five hours. The solvent was removed partially under reduced pressure and the yellow precipitate formed was collected on a filter under suction and dried under vacuum. Yield 70%. Anal. Found: C, 60.0; H, 3.81; Sn, 18.19%. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{22}N_2O_6Sn$: C, 59.19; H, 3.39; Sn, 18.3%.

9. *Dibenzoato-bis* (5, 7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato) tin(IV) was obtained, by stirring for 4 hours, a mixture of bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (1.089 g, 0.002 mole) in benzene-dichloromethane (1:1) mixture (250 ml) and benzoylperoxide (0.48 g, 0.002 mole) in benzene (30 ml). Yield, 70%. Anal. Found: C, 48.96; H, 2.88; Sn, 14.88%. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{18}N_2O_6Cl_4Sn$: C, 48.8; H, 2.289; Sn, 15.09%.

10. *Dibenzoatobis* (5, 7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato) tin(IV) was obtained by stirring for 4 hours, a mixture of bis(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (1.45 g, 0.002 mole) in benzene-dichloromethane (1:1 mixture 300 ml) and benzoyl peroxide (0.48 g, 0.002 mole) in benzene (30 ml). Yield, 70%. Anal. Found: C, 40.55; H, 2.24; Sn, 12.18%. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{18}N_2O_6Br_4Sn$: C, 39.8; H, 1.86; Sn, 12.3%.

11. *Dichlorobis* 5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV): Bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (1.039 g, 0.002 mole) in dichloromethane (100 ml) was maintained at 0-5° and stirred magnetically. Wijn's solution (i.e. ICl in acetic acid 0.81g in 50 ml) was added drop by drop in slight excess. Stirring was continued at this temperature for 30 minutes first and later at room temperature for 1 hour. Yellow solid separated was collected and purified by recrystallization from benzene. Yield, 60%. Anal. Found: C, 34.91; H, 1.64; Sn, 18.9%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Cl_6Sn$: C, 34.99; H, 1.30; Sn, 19.21%.

12. *Dichlorobis*(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) was obtained by following the above procedure, from bis (5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (1.45 g, 0.002 mole) in dichloromethane and ICl in acetic acid solution. Yield, 60%. Anal. Found: C, 27.56; H, 1.5; Sn, 14.8%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Br_4Cl_2Sn$: C, 27.2; H, 1.01, Sn, 14.97%.

13. *Monochlorotris*(8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) was obtained by following the above procedure from bis (8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (0.81 g, 0.002 mole) in dichloromethane and ICl. Yield, 40%. Anal. Found: Sn, 20.29; Cl; 5.71%. Calcd for $C_{27}H_{18}N_3O_3ClSn$: Sn, 20.25; Cl; 6.06%.

14. *Ditodobis*(8-quinolinolato)tin(IV): Bis(8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (0.81 g, 0.002 mole) in methylene chloride (25 ml) was cooled (0-5°) and iodine solution (0.508 g, 0.004 mole) in methylene chloride (30 ml) was added to it drop by drop with stirring, over a period of 20 minutes. The mixture was stirred for one hour at room temperature. The solvent was removed partially under reduced pressure. The brown solid which separated out was collected on a filter, washed with methylene chloride (5 ml) and dried under vacuum. Decomposes >250°±4. Yield, 70%. Anal. Found: C, 32.00; H, 1.91; Sn, 17.87%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{18}N_2O_2I_2Sn$: C, 32.71; H, 1.82; Sn, 17.97%.

15. *Ditodobis*(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) was obtained by following the above experimental procedure from bis (5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (1.089 g, 0.002 mole) in methylene chloride (50 ml) and iodine (0.51 g, 0.004 mole), Yield, 65%. Anal. Found: C, 26.84; H, 1.48; Sn, 14.54%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Cl_4I_2Sn$: C, 27.04; H, 1.01; Sn, 14.86%.

16. *Ditodobis* (5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) was obtained in the same way as above from bis (5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (1.45 g, 0.002 mole) in methylene chloride (75 ml) and iodine (0.51 g, 0.002 mole) in methylene chloride (30 ml). Yield, 70%. Anal. Found: C, 22.4; H, 1.1; Sn, 11.98%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Br_4I_2Sn$: C, 22.14; H, 0.82; Sn, 12.15%.

17. *Dibromobis* (5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV): Bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (1.089g, 0.002 mole) in methylene chloride (75 ml) was cooled to 0-5°. To this solution, bromine solution (0.32 g, 0.004 mole) in methylene chloride was added drop by drop with stirring over a period of 20 minutes. The temperature of the mixture was maintained at 0-5° during this period. Stirring was continued later at room temperature for another 30 minutes. Bright yellow solid that separated out was collected on a filter, washed with methylene chloride (5 ml) and dried under vacuum. Yield, 70%. Anal. Found: C, 30.9; H, 1.94; Sn, 16.17; Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Cl_4Br_2Sn$: C, 30.64; H, 1.13; Sn, 16.84%.

18. *Dibromobis* (5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) was prepared by following the above experimental procedure from bis (5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato)tin(II) (1.45 g, 0.002 mole) in methylene chloride (75 ml) and bromine (0.32 g, 0.004 mole) in methylene chloride (30 ml). Bright yellow solid that separated out was crystallised from chloroform. Yield, 70%. Anal. Found: C, 24.3; H, 1.1; Sn, 13.3%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_8N_2O_2Br_4Sn$: C, 24.47; H, 0.9; Sn, 13.45%.

In these reactions the tendency for the tin atom to achieve three coordination is apparently maintained. The quinolinol moiety presumably occupies two coordination positions characteristic of chelate formation with chlorine atom in the third position. Curran and Doskey²⁰ from their Mössbauer spectral studies concluded that the tin atom in SnCl(oxine) is probably three coordinate (Fig. I) as there is no evidence for halogen bridging to give a higher coordination number than three.

FIG. I.

On this basis, the tin atom in monochloro(5,7-dihalo-8-quinolinolato) tin(II) chelates is probably three coordinate. In the i.r. spectra of 8-quinolinol and 5,7-dihalo-8-quinolinols the broad to medium intensity band observed at ca. 3200 cm^{-1} may be attributed to inter/intra molecularly bonded OH vibration. The phenolic OH in-plane deformation vibration coupled with C-O str. mode is observed at ca. 1410 cm^{-1} and at ca. 1200 cm^{-1} . The second coupled mode expected at ca. 1200 cm^{-1} could be also located in all the substituted 8-quinolinols. The absence of these absorption bands in the spectra of the chelates, bis(8-quinolinolato) tin(II), bis(5,7-dichloro 8-quinolinolato) tin(II), bis(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato) tin(II) and bis(5,7-diiodo-8-quinolinolato) tin(II), indicates that the proton of the hydroxyl group is replaced by the metal in the chelates. Charles et al²¹ have measured the i.r. spectra of metal-8-quinolinol complexes and have shown that the aryl-oxygen vibration appearing at 1090 cm^{-1} in 8-quinolinol, shifts to higher frequency on chelation and is attributed to

the formation of an $M-O-\overset{\curvearrowright}{C}$ system. The i.r. spectra

of tin(II) chelates with 8-quinolinol and 5,7-dihalo-8-quinolinol show this characteristic vibration at ca. 1100 cm^{-1} . This indicates that both 8-quinolinolato moieties in these chelates, function as bidentate ligands, apparently increasing the coordination number of tin atom to four. Divalent tin compounds are generally expected to achieve coordination saturation at coordination number three²² as in tin(II) sulphate²³ or potassium tris (formate) stannate(II)²⁴ which have pyramidal three-coordinate tin. However, more recent structural investigations on tin(II) oxygen compounds show that simple trigonal-pyramidal geometry for tin(II) is by no means exclusive and coordination number at tin(II) can increase beyond three²⁵⁻²⁷. In tin(II) β -diketonato derivatives it was assumed on the basis of available structural data^{28,29} that β -diketonato functions as an intramolecularly coordinating bidentate ligand and the tin atom in the compounds is expected to be four-coordinate. In analogy with tin(II) β -diketonato complexes as well as bis(diethylthiocarbamate) tin(II)³⁰, the probable structure for the tin(II) bisoxinates

is likely to be a distorted trigonal bipyramid at tin in which the tin lone pair exhibits stereochemical activity, occupying an equatorial position viz.

X = H or a halogen

FIG. II

The i.r. spectra of tin (II) bisoxinates in the region 700 cm^{-1} - 300 cm^{-1} are complicated due to the absorption bands of the ligands. However, two new absorption bands which are absent in the spectra of the ligands are observed in the 450-500 cm^{-1} region and at ca. 330 cm^{-1} . The Sn-Oxygen stretching frequency is not generally readily assignable. In Sn(II) chelates investigated recently, strong to medium intense bands observed in the i.r. spectra at ca. 490-515 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$ vibrations³¹. The intense band observed in the spectrum of tin(II) methoxide at 560 cm^{-1} has been assigned by Harrison to $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$ vibration³². Accordingly, the strong to medium intense bands present in the spectra of bis(8-quinolinolato) tin(II) and bis(5,7-dihalo-8-quinolinolato) tin(II) have been ascribed to $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$ vibrations. Of considerable interest would be the frequency of tin-nitrogen coordinate bond stretching mode in Sn(II) chelates. The medium to weak intensity absorption bands observed at ca. 330 cm^{-1} have been tentatively assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn} \leftarrow \text{N})$ vibrations in analogy with recent assignments by Nakamoto in some tin(II) complexes containing tinnitrogen bond³³.

The Sn-Cl symmetric and anti-symmetric stretching modes of the bent triatomic SnCl_2 observed in the i.r. spectrum at ca. 350 cm^{-1} and at ca. 330 cm^{-1} respectively, on complex formation shift slightly to lower frequencies. The magnitude of the shift is of the order of ~ 7 cm^{-1} . In the spectra of monochloro oxinato-tin(II) chelates, SnLCl, the weak broad bands observed at ca. 322 cm^{-1} may be attributed to antisymmetric Sn-Cl str. vibration. The symmetric Sn-Cl str. vibration apparently is masked due to the presence of other vibrations. The Sn-Br and Sn-I vibrations in the spectra of Sn(IV) chelates could not be located, for the spectra were recorded upto 300 cm^{-1} only.

TABLE 1—ULTRAVIOLET AND VISIBLE ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF TIN(II) AND TIN(IV) CHELATES WITH 8-QUINOLINOL AND SUBSTITUTED 8-QUINOLINOLS.

S. No.	Compound	Solvent	λ_{max} (nm)	$\epsilon(M^{-1}cm^{-1})$ $\times 10^{-3}$
1.	8-Hydroxyquinolinol	Methanol	310	2.39
			256	
			231	
2.	5,7-Dichloro-8-quinolinol	CCl_4	320	2.64
			337	
3.	5,7-Dibromo-8-quinolinol	$CHCl_3$	337	3.00
			335	
4.	5,7-Diiodo-8-quinolinol	Alcohol	335	1.9
			375	
5.	Sn(Ox) ₂	Methanol	380	0.85
			D. M. F.	
			CH_2Cl_2	
			385	
6.	Sn(dichloroOx) ₂	Benzene	395	1.35
			420	
			410	
			265	
7.	Sn(dibromoOx) ₂	Benzene	415	4.27
			Methanol	
			255	
			265	
8.	Sn(diiodoOx) ₂	DMF	400	3.53
			420	
9.	Sn(dichloroOx) ₂ Cl ₂	Benzene	420	3.93
			420	
10.	Sn(dibromoOx) ₂ Cl ₂	-do-	420	2.97
			417	
11.	Sn(OX) ₂ Cl	-do-	417	5.83
			415	
12.	Sn(dichloroOx) ₂ Br ₂	-do-	415	3.66
			420	
13.	Sn(dibromoOx) ₂ Br ₂	-do-	420	1.26
			410	
14.	Sn(dichloroOx) ₂ I ₂	-do-	410	3.64
			415	
15.	Sn(dibromoOx) ₂ I ₂	Benzene	415	5.89
			395	
16.	Sn(oxine) ₂ I ₂	-do-	395	2.09
			243	
17.	Sn(Ox)Cl	Methanol	243	2.7
			257	
			26	
			390	
18.	Sn(dibromoOx)Cl	Benzene	415	2.3
			412	
19.	Sn(dichloroOx)Cl	Benzene	412	1.525
			267	

* HOx=8-quinolinol

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The ultraviolet and visible absorption spectral data for the tin chelates along with the ligands are presented in Table 1. The absorption bands of the anion of 8-quinolinol and some of its chelates have been assigned by Perkampus and Körtum²⁴ and according to these authors the absorption band appearing at 322 nm is the low energy transition and the one at 317.5 nm is the high energy transition. The shift to longer wave lengths of 320 nm absorption of 8-quinolinol in the spectra of oxinatometal complexes is generally considered to be a reliable indication for the presence of a chelating oxine ligand²⁴⁻²⁷. In the U.V. and visible spectra of tin(II) bisoxinates as well as in dihalogenobis(oxinato or substituted oxinato)Sn(IV) chelates, the low-energy absorption band in the ligands (ca. 320-340 nm) is shifted to ca. 375-420 nm and is observed as a strong broad band indicating the presence of chelated 8-quinolinolato or substituted 8-quinolinolato groups in the compounds. The strong band observed at ca. 265 nm in the chelates and also in the ligands is mainly due to the benzene ring vibrations^{24,28}.

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